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Research article

**PREVALANCE OF ANXIETY AMONG THE MEDICAL
STUDENTS OF ALLAMA IQBAL MEDICAL COLLEGE
LAHORE**Ayesha Riaz¹, Maria Batool², Aisha Akbar³¹ Sir Gangaraam Hospital, Lahore, ² Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, ³ Karachi Medical & Dental College, Karachi.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the prevalence of anxiety and depression among medical students.**Material and Methods:** A total of 120 students were included in this study. A predefined questionnaire was served. Data collected was analyzed with SPSS 23.0.**Results:** Out of 120, eighty two students returned the questionnaire. The response rate was 68.33%. There were forty nine (59.75%) female students and thirty three (40.24%) male students. The mean age of the students was 23.15±2.25 years. Regarding the frequency of anxiety, it was highest in final year students (88%), 79% in the fourth year, 67% in the third year, 49% in the second year and 40% in first-year students.**Conclusion:** A large number of the medical students suffer from anxiety and depression throughout their academic career. It can lead to physical and mental health problems leading to poor performance in studies.**Keywords:** Anxiety, medical education, distress, emotional behavior, depression.**Corresponding author:****Ayesha Riaz,**

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INTRODUCTION:

According to the studies, the emotional condition of an individual involved in unhappiness and sadness is considered as anxiety. It varies among different individuals from mild to intense and temporary or permanent in nature. Anxiety can lead to the depression among the individuals, leading to certain complications i.e. anorexia, suicidal thoughts or mental disorders etc. This anxiety may happen due to some stress or pressure at workplace, traumatic events or some personal issues [1,2].

Regarding the medical education, it is considered as the toughest education throughout the world due to its hectic ward and emergency routines as well as difficult subjects. In medical students, the prevalence of anxiety or depression may be higher than other students. There are certain factors that cause this high prevalence. These include depraved behavior of patient attendants, non-availability of basic facilities, and the overburden of patients, lesser resources and lack of sleep. It will ultimately cause poor efficiency of health professionals and students leading to the collapsed health system [2-4].

Numerous studies have been conducted on the assessment of anger among health professionals and medical students [5-7]. The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence of anxiety in medical students in different classes. This study will help in analyzing the factors leading to certain levels of anxiety and will enable us in formulating strategies to minimize these triggering factors hence leading to more productive health professionals.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore. One hundred and twenty male and female students from different classes were included in this study. A predefined questionnaire was distributed after taking informed consent. Different questions regarding anxiety, depression and certain triggering factors was asked. Confidentiality of the participant was ensured. The data collected was analyzed in SPSS Ver. 23.0. The qualitative variables were expressed as numbers and percentages, quantitative variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

Out of one hundred and twenty students, eighty two students returned the questionnaire. The response rate was 68.33%. There were forty nine (59.75%) female students and thirty three (40.24%) male students. The mean age of the students was 23.15 ± 2.25 years, minimum age noticed was 20 years and maximum age noticed was 26 years. There were 21 students (25.60%) from final year, 19 (23.17%) from the fourth year, 16 (19.51%) from the third year, 14 (17.07%) from the second year and 12 (14.63%) from the first year.

Regarding the frequency of anxiety, it was highest in final year students (88%), 79% in the fourth year, 67% in the third year, 49% in the second year and 40% in first-year students. Different aspects of their anxiety or depression are expressed in the table.

Class	Impaired physical Health (%)	Effect on appetite (%)	Poor Decision Power (%)	Shouting (%)	Relationship issues (%)	Easy irritation (%)
1 st year	23	32	45	61	8	23
2 nd year	12	8	21	32	12	12
3 rd year	67	34	23	19	15	67
4 th year	9	55	59	42	20	9
Final year	19	41	87	75	45	19

Reasons of the anxiety were tough examinations (68%), irregular ward routines (54%), hostel life (19%), the behavior of seniors (14%), bad relations with the opposite gender (12%), and poor teaching methodology (8%).

DISCUSSION:

In this study, a larger number of students was experiencing from different levels of anxiety and depression. The most interesting fact to be noted is

that, it was more prevalent (88%) in final year medical students. There are multiple reasons for this high prevalence such as tough routine due to difficult subjects and hectic ward or emergency routines. Due

to this hectic routine, their meals are often disturbed and that they have limited or no chances of recreations or enjoyment. Other causes leading to the anxiety and depression are poor methodology of the teachers and rude behavior of senior doctors.

Studies already conducted in Pakistan show a higher number of depression cases among medical students. The studies by Inam et al., Jadoon et al., and Bayram et al., reported similar findings in their studies³⁻⁵. Some reasons for depression in their studies include assignments, dedicated and demanding studies, family pressures, hostel life and fear of future.

Dahlin and Saipanich in their studies stated that this anger and stress imposes certain negative effects on students^{6,7} i.e. they become more prone to physical and mental health issues. In our study, certain effects of included irritation on minor issues, impaired appetite, compromised decision power, shouting and bad relationships with other students.

This study reveals interesting factors that a medical student had to face throughout their academic career. These factors should be addressed by institutional administration and relevant policies must be formulated.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the medical students suffer from anxiety and depression throughout their academic career. It can lead to physical and mental health problems leading to poor performance in the studies.

Contribution of authors:

Ayesha Riaz: Writing the introduction and Methodology section

Maria Batool: Data Collection, writing limitations and conclusion section

Aisha Akbar: Writing the results and discussion section

REFERENCES:

1. The main symptoms of the AHA-syndrome: relationships between anger, hostility and aggression in a normal population. Ramirez JM, Rodríguez A, Manuel J. <https://eprints.ucm.es/8406/AHA-Syndrome> Cardiovasc Dis. 2009;321:16–29.
2. Longitudinal study of adolescent blood pressures, health habits, stress and anger. Health values. Groër M, Thomas S, Droppleman P, Younger MS. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1995-16851-001> J Health Behav Educ Promot. 1994;18:25–33.
3. Inam SN, Saqib A, Alam E. J Pak Med Assoc. Vol. 53. Journal-Pakistan Medical Association; 2003. Prevalence of anxiety and depression

among medical students of private university; pp. 44–47.

4. Anxiety and depression among medical students: a cross-sectional study. Jadoon NA, Yaqoob R, Raza A, Shehzad MA, Zeshan SC. <https://jpma.org.pk/article-details/2243>. J Pak Med Assoc. 2010;60:699–702.
5. The prevalence and socio-demographic correlations of depression, anxiety and stress among a group of university students. Bayram N, Bilgel N. Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol. 2008;43:667–672.
6. Dahlin M, Joneborg N, Runeson B. Stress and depression among medical students: A cross-sectional study. Medical education. 2005 Jun;39(6):594-604.
7. Saipanish R. Stress among medical students in a Thai medical school. Medical teacher. 2003 Jan 1;25(5):502-6.